

PRAGMATIC ISSUES OF TRANSLATING ETHNOGRAPHS IN NOVELS FROM UZBEK INTO ENGLISH

Firuzabonu Bekmurodova

PhD researcher, NUUz, Uzbekistan

Abstract. *This article explores the pragmatic issues involved in translating ethnographisms from Uzbek into English, focusing on literary works. Ethnographisms, or words specific to national traditions and customs, play a crucial role in shaping a culture's identity and are deeply embedded in the vocabulary of a language. However, translating these ethnographisms presents challenges due to differences in cultural contexts and pragmatic implications between languages. The study emphasizes the importance of achieving pragmatic equivalence in translation, particularly in literary works where cultural concepts are paramount.*

Keywords: *Ethnolinguistics, ethnographisms, translation, pragmatic equivalence, cultural context, literary translation.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada etnografizmlarni o'zbek tilidan ingliz tiliga tarjima qilish bilan bog'liq pragmatik jihatlar o'rganilib, badiiy asarlarga e'tibor qaratiladi. Etnografizmlar yoki milliy an'ana va urf-odatlariga xos so'zlar madaniyatning o'ziga xosligini shakllantirishda hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi va tilning lug'at tarkibida asosiy qatlamlardan biri hisoblanadi. Biroq, bu etnografizmlarni tarjima qilish madaniy kontekstlardagi farqlar va tillar o'rtasidagi pragmatik ta'sirlar tufayli qiyinchiliklar tug'diradi. Tadqiqot tarjimada, xususan, milliy-madaniy tushunchalar ishtirok etgan badiiy asarlarda pragmatik ekvivalentlikka erishish yo'llari haqida so'z borgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Etnolingvistika, etnografizm, tarjima, pragmatik ekvivalentlik, madaniy kontekst, badiiy tarjima.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются прагматические аспекты перевода этнографизмов с узбекского на английский язык, с акцентом на литературные произведения. Этнографизмы, или слова, характерные для национальных традиций и обычаев, играют важную роль в формировании культурной идентичности и глубоко вкоренены в словарный запас языка. Однако перевод этих этнографизмов представляет собой сложную задачу из-за различий в культурных контекстах и прагматических последствиях между языками. В статье подчеркивается важность достижения прагматической эквивалентности в переводе, особенно в литературных произведениях, где культурные концепты имеют первостепенное значение.*

Ключевые слова: *Этнолингвистика, этнографизмы, перевод, прагматическая эквивалентность, культурный контекст, художественный перевод.*

It is well known that groups embodying customs and principles come together within a common framework to carry out the function of shaping a people's culture. The study of traditions and customs is relevant to various scientific disciplines as well as linguistics. One of the areas of modern linguistics that has recently emerged and is drawing attention from scientists is ethnolinguistics. Not much research is done in this area of science.

While it is regarded as a separate scientific area, M.S. Yangelova claims that the term ethnolinguistics is strongly tied to the ideas of ethnography and ethnology. When used narrowly, ethnolinguistics is defined as the area of linguistics that focuses on the connections between language and national mindset, folk art, and culture. Some sources state that customs around child

naming have been investigated via the lens of ethnography[6]. These studies, however, only represent a small portion of the studies that highlight the ethnographic traits of various countries.

Lexical units associated with traditions, conventions, and rituals are referred to as ethnographisms in the fields of ethnolinguistics and ethnography. R.Kasimova states that “lexical units, or ethnographisms, hold a significant position in language and make up the vocabulary level of language construction”[2;28]. “Ethnolinguistics” is the name of the field that examines ethnographisms at the vocabulary level.

Words specific to national traditions and customs occupy the main place in the vocabulary of the language. The lexical-semantic features of the so-called ethnographic lexicon - the lexical units representing the national values and traditions of the people - have been the focus of attention of several scientists. In particular, the scientist M.S. Yangelova divided the ethnographisms into two large lexical-semantic groups and classified them as follows:

- material-cultural ethnographisms: *supra, table, kapgir, khontakhta, etc.*;
- spiritual-cultural ethnographic terms: *wedding, khatna, mavlud, hinabandon, etc.*[6;35];

Comparative linguistics is strongly associated with the field of translation. Although translation is a secondary and creative process that is now seen as a bridge connecting different language cultures, it may be partially accurate to believe that a translator’s only job is to convert a text’s content from one language into another. Translation studies study thus highlights the importance of considering pragmatic factors of translation in addition to morphological, syntactic, and semantic components. This article also covers the pragmatics of literary translation as well as the translation of ethnographisms into English using pragmatic equivalence.

The issues stemming from the fact that the unique pragmatic qualities of words reflecting Uzbek national culture in literary works are often overlooked in English translations are as follows:

- Lack of suitable equivalents for culturally specific words in the target text (TT) compared to the original text (AT).
- Failure to consider the contextual pragmatic meaning of ethnographic terms during direct translation.
- Incorrect interpretation of contextual meanings and implied meanings.
- Absence of equivalents for certain religious ethnographic terms in the TT.
- Ignoring the multiple meanings of certain ethnographic terms during translation.
- Neglecting the specific characteristics of ethnographic language units borrowed from other languages in the AT.
- Literal translation of occasionalisms and ethnographic archaisms with cultural significance in literary works.

The lack of TT counterparts for the ethnographisms utilised in the AT text is one of the primary issues with literary translation. In these circumstances, translators translated these ethnographisms using a variety of techniques:

- Assimilation: *dastarkhan*, a traditional tablecloth spread out for meals;
- Transcription (transliteration): *pilaf, plov/pilaf*;
- Hypo-hyperonymic translation: *doira – musical instrument*;
- Descriptive translation: *offering a thorough explanation of national-cultural terms*.

Nevertheless, considering the pragmatics of translation, these approaches may not always yield a satisfactory translation. For example, in the excerpt below, “*qarshi quda*” involves ethnographism, a unit that is completely unfamiliar to the English language and culture. Also, the

contextual meaning of the word “silliq” (smooth) and the fact that the word “kelin” (kelin) has a national color were not taken into account in the translation, and the translation did not fully provide a pragmatic effect for the addressee:

In Uzbek: *Qarshi quda bo'lmoq uchun qizliq va o'g'ullik havlini uchratish va buning ustiga “naslu nasabda tekislik”, olinadig'an kelinning silliqina bo'lishi – ana shunday mushkilotlar orqasida ikki yil chamasi Naimaning umri sarg'ayib o'tdi.* [3;32]

In English: *She wanted to engage Naima with someone and then to find somebody for Mahdum from that family. In order to find an appropriate family **with good manner** which had both a son and a daughter.* [4;28]

The Uzbek language explanatory dictionary lists the following meanings for the word “silliq” (smooth):

- (1) flat, hilly, undulating;
- (2) slippery, glassy;
- (3) smooth, polished;
- (4) Movable - s. t. Handsome, elegant, beautiful;
- (5) Mobile - flawless, fluent (about language, style, speech, etc.);
- (6) Pleasant, not harsh, gentle;
- (7) Without issue; as you wish, without obstacles; fluffy; careless;
- (8) Silent; without realising it;
- (9) Evenly, evenly, smoothly, noiselessly [7].

The phrase “*kelinning silliqina bo'lishi*” in the aforementioned work extract has multiple connotations intended by the author. Although in SLT the author tried to convey (4), (6), and (7) meanings, in the English translation only meaning (6) is indicated.

There are multiple reasons why we consider the term “*kelin*” to be an ethnographism. Firstly, its role and pragmatic implications in Uzbek culture differ significantly from the English concepts of “bride” or “daughter-in-law”. In Uzbek culture, a “*kelin*” is someone who serves her husband and his family, shows respect to all family members, takes part in household chores and child-rearing. In contrast, in English culture, she is considered a full member of the family with equal rights. Therefore, translators often interpret the term “daughter-in-law” more generally as “appropriate family” to capture its broader cultural context.

Considering that the term “*kelin*” in Uzbek language has varying meanings depending on context, it's inaccurate to simply label it as a straightforward ethnographic lexeme. Its meaning can change based on context, carrying pragmatic effects and implied meanings. Thus, we suggest calling such terms “contextual ethnographisms”. We define contextual ethnographism as a word or phrase characteristic of a specific culture or tradition, which acts as an ethnographic term only in certain contexts, reflecting the cultural characteristics.

Given the contextual nature of the term “*kelin*” as a contextual ethnographism, to enhance its pragmatic impact on the reader, we recommend translating it as follows:

*She wanted Naima to marry with a man at the same time who also has a sister for Mahdum. It took her almost 2 years to find an appropriate family **with an ideal daughter who meets all of her criteria (including social status, appearance and behavior).***

Consequently, in order to achieve pragmatic equivalence, the translator must possess an impeccable understanding of the cultural components associated with the setting and be able to accurately represent each of these contextual characteristics in the translation. The translator needs to pay close attention to cultural differences, how they are presented in the literary work, and how

much the author has considered the usage of certain linguistic units in order to prevent misunderstandings or misinterpretations. Cultural and social content of novels can also evolve over time. In some situations, the ethnographisms that were incorporated into literary text created several centuries ago may have become antiquated or gone out of use in language.

For example, the words “*panjshanbalik*” or “*ozodliq*” used in A. Qadiri’s work “*Mehrobdan Chayon*” (Scorpion from the Altar) are used only in this work, and there are no explanations and examples of them in other sources. In this case, “*panjshanbalik oshlari*” was used 6 times in this work, and “*ozodliq (oshlari)*” was used 9 times, and it was necessary to translate the meaning of these occasionalisms from the contexts in which they were involved. However, in the presentation of these lexical units in English, the fact that “*panjshanbalik*” is simply translated as “Thursday, *Thursdayship*” and “*ozodliq*” as “freedom” or omitted in the translation is the reason for the loss of the pragmatic meaning understood from the context, the national coloring and original meaning of occasionalism. In our opinion, revealing the contextual meanings of these words through the method of expansion serves to convey the writer’s pragmatic intention to the reader.

According to the context, we can see that “*panjshanbalik oshlari*” and “*ozodliq oshlari*” not only mean Uzbek national dish “*osh*”, or “*dish/meal*” in general, but also have other meanings in the following cases:

A) – *in the meaning of money:*

Buni ham qo‘yib turayliq, Nigor oyim yigirma-o‘ttuz qizni o‘qutib ulardan tushkan “ozodliq” va “panjshanbalik” pullarga ham ega bo‘lolmas, har kun deyarlik muhtarab maxdum pochchag‘a hisobini batamom topshurib turishqa majbur edi.

B) *In the meaning of gift, especially, cloth:*

Ammo “ozodliq” masalasida bolalardan hech kimni ham afu etmas, boy bolasig‘a “ozodliq” lozim bo‘lg‘an bo‘lsa albatta undirishka, kambag‘al bolasidan mumkin qadar uzib olishg‘a harakat qilar; bolalar Haftiyak, Qur‘on, So‘fi Olloyor va shunga o‘xshash kitob boshlasalar ozodliq majburiy, maktabdan ma‘zun bo‘lg‘anlarning ziyofat qilib maxdumga sarupo berishlari qoidada bor bo‘lsa ham, lekin aksar bolalar bu to‘g‘rida domlani – “ana-mana” bilan aldab ketarlar,

A) *In the meaning of the meal:*

Ikki haftasiz palovni ko‘rmaslar (ozodliq oshlari albatta mundan mustasno), ko‘b ovqatlari ubra, tuppi, mastaba, qo‘g‘urma sho‘rba bo‘lar edi.

From the above 3 different contexts, we can conclude that “*panjshanbalik*” and “*ozodliq*” (*osh*) can be interpreted as a contribution in the form of money in example 1, food in example 3 and in the meaning of gift in example 2 because the students learned from the teacher. Thus, it is necessary to pay attention to their contextual meaning in the translation as it is regarded one of the crucial factors in delivering the writer’s message to the reader.

The Uzbek literary works we have examined encapsulate Uzbek national traditions and values deeply rooted in ancient traditions. Consequently, translating such works from Uzbek to English is fundamentally distinct from other types of translation, presenting a highly intricate process. Achieving pragmatic equivalence in the translation of these works relies on implicatures and maintaining consistency with national cultural contexts. The accurate interpretation of implicatures forms the foundation for adequate translation.

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